

MARINEWIND

Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)

1/11/2022 – 31/10/2025

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Project 101075572 — MARINEWIND

D5.1: Strategic Communication and Dissemination Plan

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D5.1 Strategic Communication and Dissemination Plan (SCDP) is produced in the aim of Task 5.1 of work package 5 related to the communication of the MARINEWIND project. **This work package aims at wide spreading information about the MARINEWIND activities and findings to the identified audience and exploiting its activities beyond the end of the project.** To support this, a Strategic Communication and Dissemination Plan is produced.

The task leader with the support of all partners will develop this SCDP that will establish comprehensive guidelines for the Consortium regarding all project communication and dissemination activities.

The Plan will define the communication goals, targeted audience, approaches (content and channels) and timings that MARINEWIND partners will follow to optimise the dissemination of the project's ongoing results and ensure the visibility of the project activities and its outcomes. The Plan will contain all the local, national, and European events that could be useful for the communication and dissemination activities. The Communication and Dissemination Plan will be updated during the lifetime of the project to improve its effectiveness.

It is important to note that, as stated in Article 17.2 of the Grant Agreement, "communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must **acknowledge EU support** and display the **European flag (emblem)** and **funding statement** (translated into local languages, where appropriate)".

"The EU flag and funding statement must be displayed in a way that is easily visible for the public and with sufficient prominence", as stated in the European Commission online manual.

Figure 1. European flag and funding statement

Additionally, as stated in Article 17.3 of the Grant Agreement "Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

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2. INTRODUCTION

2.1 PURPOSE AND SCOPE OF THE DELIVERABLE

MARINEWIND's Strategic Communication and Dissemination Plan is a comprehensive guide designed to effectively provide specific information about the project to various audiences in a strategic and effective manner. Its objective is to inform and enable identified stakeholder groups to utilize and benefit from the project's outcomes, thereby maximizing its impact. The plan includes communication activities that involve specific measures for promoting the project to engage a critical mass of stakeholders.

To achieve this, campaigns will be designed and implemented throughout the project lifetime. These campaigns will build upon the promotion mix that focuses on creating awareness and persuading the audience to be engaged. The aim is to build traction among the target audience efficiently and communicate the project's benefits to society.

This Plan – drafted at the beginning of the project – is coordinated by the lead partner of the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Work Package – WavEC Offshore Renewables – with validation of the coordinator and will have input from all involved partners.

The Communication Plan of MARINEWIND will be regularly updated during the project's lifetime to align with its progress and improve its effectiveness. The plan will include monitoring activities to ensure that MARINEWIND's communication activities have been effective and reached the various existing audiences.

All information and messages shared externally will follow the European Commission (EC) funding guidelines and will follow the methodology around the following five dimensions:

- WHAT: The main project's outcomes to be disseminated, communicated and exploited;
- WHO: Identification of the target audiences to be informed and involved in the project's activities;
- WHAT FOR: Definition of the foreseen outcomes of the dissemination and communication activities and expected impact per type of stakeholders (KPIs);
- HOW: Type of Communication and Dissemination tools, activities and channels tailored to the intended beneficiaries;
- WHEN: Timeline for their implementation and action plans for the consortium for each type of activity.

2.2 PROJECT SUMMARY

MARINEWIND is a 36-month coordination and support action that will identify bottlenecks and potential opportunities to strengthen floating offshore wind's technology FOWT role in delivering innovative solutions to system integration and will consider how best to integrate such a system by exploring the market, policy and regulations issues, social, financial, and techno-economic optimal solutions, and provision for storage and flexibility recommendations.

MARINEWIND will use pilot studies located in Portugal, UK, Greece, Spain, and Italy, called MARINEWIND Labs, to analyse political, societal, environmental, technological, and financial barriers and enablers. The Labs will be studied to identify and verify the challenges and opportunities for commercialising offshore wind in European countries and their replicability globally. Furthermore, they will transfer knowledge from established experiences to potential FOWT sites in various planning or implementation stages. The MARINEWIND Labs apply co-creation and survey results involving stakeholders from industry, academia, public authorities, civil society, and green innovation.

The results will be presented on a webGIS platform, providing customized information on FOWT for different stakeholders based on their needs, interests, goals and locations, strengthening the uptake of FOWT in society by making key information more accessible.

3. STRATEGY & METHODOLOGY

3.1 OVERVIEW OF THE STRATEGY

The MARINEWIND Strategic Communication and Dissemination Plan follows the so called 5Ws and 1H communication model shown on Figure 2. This model addresses the following questions: What are the main messages? Who constitutes the intended audience or audiences? What is the communication's purpose? Who are the contributors? What methods will be employed or How will the messages be disseminated? and When will these actions be executed?

Figure 2. MARINEWIND Communication and Dissemination Strategy model

3.2 WHAT: KEY MESSAGE

The MARINEWIND project may have several messages to its audience or audiences because different audiences may require different messages. In this plan we will define the (short) key message of the project to answer what we plan to disseminate.

The main message of the MARINEWIND project is the following:

MARINEWIND will support the investment of both private sector and public authorities in FOWT while accelerating their commercialisation and identifying critical environmental and societal support and solutions to techno-economic barriers to their wide deployment in various European geographical areas. This short text will be used at the social media accounts.

3.3 WHOM: THE AUDIENCE

MARINEWIND project covers a wide range of audiences. A preliminary assessment indicates that the stakeholders can be divided according to the Quintuple Helix approach which involves:

- **Industry:** FOWT installation developers, engineering companies, tech/project developers, trade associations (fisheries and tourism);
- **Academia:** Scientific Community;
- **Public authorities:** at European (EC, European associations e.g. ICLEI, ERRIN), national (Ministries for Energy, for Industry and for Environment) and local level (Regional authorities), maritime transport authorities, policy makers;
- **Civil society:** NGOs civil society organisations and citizens at large.
- **Green innovation:** SMEs, public/private financial investors, insurers, ecologists, environmental organisations, natural parks.
- **Other EU funded projects and initiatives.**

Partners will support the Task 1.2 leader in order to create a rich database of contacts in order to contact the relevant targeted audience.

3.4 WHY: THE PURPOSE

The ultimate ambition of MARINEWIND is to support investment of both private sector and public authorities in FOWT while accelerating their commercialisation and identifying critical environmental, societal support and solutions to techno-economic barriers to their wide deployment in various European geographical areas.

The objectives and impacts of the MARINEWIND project will assist and support the European Commission to reach the EU's goal of climate neutrality by 2050 via the implementation of the EU Strategy on Offshore Renewable Energy. The MARINEWIND project will contribute to generate substantial investments in FOWT by a) facilitating the exchange of knowledge in terms of methodology b) providing expert advice on how to cut down deployment times and accelerate time to market c) contributing to lower market barriers and increasing societal acceptance, facilitating the interaction with other sea users such as fisheries or maritime traffic d) providing insights on how to minimize the environmental impact.

3.5 WHO: CONTRIBUTORS

All the MARINEWIND partners will be contributors to the communication and dissemination activities under the overall management of WP5 leader and validation of the coordinator.

Each partner will contribute to:

- Identify relevant information to share (e.g. events, publications, activities' development and other news, etc.);
- Inform about news for the project website and social media platforms;
- Promote MARINEWIND at events and exhibitions as speakers or participants.

3.6 WHEN: TIMING

An annexed table of performance indicators, including KPIs, has been developed (see ANNEX I) to monitor the information produced and disseminated throughout the duration of the project. All project activities will be regularly monitored and adjusted as needed.

3.7 HOW: THE METHOD / CHANNELS AND TOOLS

To ensure the impact of the MARINEWIND project on society, environment, and economy, the consortium will utilize and promote the project results during and after its duration.

To raise awareness among diverse audiences, the project will utilize various communication channels and tools, including the project website, social media, press releases, videos/infographics, general flyers, posters, roll-ups, and multimedia material. The SCDP is adaptable and can incorporate additional tools and channels as the project evolves according to stakeholders' and partners' needs and interests.

To share knowledge about the project, conferences, events, publications, technical flyers, brochures, presentations, infographics, and webinars will be utilized.

ANNEX I outlines the actions and KPIs for monitoring performance, while ANNEX II presents key national and/or international conferences, congresses, workshops, fairs, etc., where project partners can communicate project activities and disseminate the results obtained.

The following sub-sections will describe the main communication and dissemination channels, and ANNEX I will detail all actions and KPIs.

3.7.1 Brand identity: Logo & Templates

A recognizable visual identity will be designed at the initial stage of the project. It will comprise brand guidelines, colors and font codes, and the logo variants needed for all applicable online or offline channels and collaterals.

- ❖ **KPIs:** #1 brand identity kit
- ❖ **Target:** All Stakeholders
- ❖ **Date:** M1

Figure 3. MARINEWIND logo colour and black & white version

3.7.2 Project Website

The project website, accessible at www.marinewindproject.eu, will serve as the primary communication tool. It will feature current news and events relevant to the project and be linked to individual webpages of consortium members.

The website is structured into the following pages:

- Home (Short overview about the project, partner logos, news and events, social media, privacy and cookies policy and funding)
- Activities (Information about the several work packages of the project)
- Reports (Deliverables and other non-confidential information about the project will be available)
- Partners (Short information about the partners, logos, and link to website)
- News & Events (Diverse information about the project's activities, events, and other useful information)
- Contacts (Contact form for those who would like to contact the Consortium)
- The project website will foresee a specific section to host the webGIS (Geographic Information System) tool (D4.1).

The website will be linked to Google Analytics to track the number of visitors to the website, the duration of the visit, locations or devices used for browsing the website and other useful information.

MARINEWIND will respect the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU) 2016/679 and introduce the Cookies Policy to its website.

- ❖ **KPIs:** #1 website
- ❖ **Specific KPI's:** >3.000 visits >27 countries reached
- ❖ **Target:** All Stakeholders
- ❖ **Date:** M6

3.7.3 Social Media

Social networking channels will be essential for the project to reach a wider audience and have immediate feed-back on its actions. It will also drive traffic to the website where further information is available to all. MARINEWIND is going to use LinkedIn and Twitter channels.

CHANNELS

The following social media channels of the project are available:

LINKEDIN

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/marinewind>

TWITTER

https://twitter.com/marinewind_eu

@marinewind_eu

The Consortium will take an active role in disseminating project news through its own channels, ensuring that MARINEWIND reaches the widest possible audience.

HASHTAGS

The following hashtags can be used to increase posts' visibility:

#offshorewindenergy #floatingoffshorewind #renewableenergy #offshorewind #floatingoffshore #renewables

The following hashtag and tags from the Funding agency and Partners can be used:

MANDATORY		LINKEDIN	TWITTER
Mandatory when possible	EU support	@CINEA - European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency #horizoneurope	@cinea_eu @HorizonEU
	Partners	@APRE - Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea @Sener @Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL @WavEC - Offshore Renewables @Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche @Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico - RSE SpA @Europêche @University of York @Energy Systems Catapult	@apre_it #sener @q_planintl @WavecOfficial @CNRsocial @RSEnergetico @EuropecheOrg @uniofyork @energysyscat

Social media communication will be monitored to increase its effectiveness.

- ❖ **KPIs:** #2 channels (LinkedIn and Twitter)
- ❖ **Specific KPI's:** >5 social media campaigns, > 1.000 followers, > 500 posts
- ❖ **Target:** All Stakeholders
- ❖ **Date:** M6

3.7.4 Flyer, Roll up and Posters

MARINEWIND intends to create a range of marketing materials, including two project flyers, two roll-ups, and a minimum of two posters, to attract the interest of attendees at events and exhibitions or to distribute at stakeholder meetings. These materials will be available in electronic format and can be printed as required.

- ❖ **KPIs:** #2 flyers, #2 roll-ups, >2 posters
- ❖ **Specific KPI's:** 500 flyers distributed in at least 5 languages included English (for the 5 Labs)
- ❖ **Target:** All Stakeholders
- ❖ **Date:** version 1: M6, version 2: M22

3.7.5 Infographics

To assist in the project's activities, dissemination, and communication, infographics will be produced throughout the project's lifespan. These materials will be made available on social media platforms and the project website to maximize their reach.

Additionally, one factsheet of the Action Plan for public acceptance is planned, one booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations in at least 5 languages included English (for the 5 Labs) and more than 10 promotional banners will be produced.

- ❖ **KPIs:** >5 infographics
- ❖ **Specific KPI's:** #1 factsheet of the Action Plan for public acceptance, #1 Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations in at least 5 languages included English (for the 5 Labs), >10 promotional banners.
- ❖ **Target:** All Stakeholders, in particular policymaker, civil society, businesses
- ❖ **Date:** M12

3.7.6 Multimedia Material

A MARINEWIND promotional video plus additional short videos and clips for the website and social media will be produced to give an overview of the results and achievements throughout the project in a simple visual way.

- ❖ **KPIs:** #1 promotional video, #2 video teasers.
- ❖ **Target:** All Stakeholders
- ❖ **Date:** M12

3.7.7 Conferences & Events and publication

The project's results will be presented by consortium partners at relevant external events that are linked to their specific competencies and expertise. These events will be held at both European and national levels, in countries where the labs are located. The events include EUSEW, European Maritime Day, WindEurope, European Week for Regions and Cities, ICLEI's conferences and events, FOWT conferences, EERA JP Wind, European Energy Association events, WavEC Seminar annual seminars, RenewableUK, etc. A draft list of upcoming events is provided in ANNEX II.

In addition to these events, the project's progress and outcomes will be disseminated through more than six press releases. These press releases will be available on the project website's news section. Moreover, over six articles will be produced for non-technical audiences and published online in newspapers, magazines, television, or radio. These articles will be linked to the project website and promoted via the MARINEWIND social media accounts.

Towards the end of the project, a final event will be organised to present the project outcomes to the European Commission and other relevant stakeholders. MARINEWIND aims to have at least 80 participants from the Quintuple Helix.

- ❖ **KPI's:** >6 speeches at events and conferences (live and online), >6 Articles in newspapers, magazines, television, or radio, >6 Press releases, #1 Final event.
- ❖ **Specific KPI's:** >6 Press releases to more than 10.000 contacts, #1 Final event to present MARINEWIND outcomes to the European Commission and other relevant stakeholders attended by at least 80 participants for the Quintuple Helix.
- ❖ **Target:** All Stakeholders

- ❖ **Date:** M12-36, Final event M34

3.7.8 Webinars

To further promote the project's results, informative webinars will be organized to connect with particularly relevant stakeholders, such as Policy makers and public authorities. These webinars will provide a platform for project partners to share the latest findings, discuss the benefits of the project, and answer any questions stakeholders may have.

By organizing these webinars, the project team will be able to engage with a wider audience and build stronger relationships with stakeholders. They will be able to receive feedback, suggestions, and insights from stakeholders who have a specific interest in the project's results.

Overall, informative webinars are an excellent way to connect with stakeholders and promote the project's results.

- ❖ **KPI's:** #2 webinars
- ❖ **Specific KPI's:** #2 informative webinars in the 5 languages included English (for the 5 Labs) (>250 participants in total)
- ❖ **Target:** Policy makers and public authorities
- ❖ **Date:** M12-34

3.7.9 Stakeholders database

Partners will support the Task 1.2 leader to create a rich database of contacts (ethical issues already considered in Task 4.3) in order to contact the relevant targeted audience in particular for the co-creation events (Task 1.3).

- ❖ **KPI's:** #1 database
- ❖ **Specific KPI's:** >1.000 contacts
- ❖ **Target:** Partners' Networks, EU and National Projects and initiatives
- ❖ **Date:** M12

3.7.10 Clustering with other projects and initiatives

To enhance the impact of the MARINEWIND project, the consortium aims to identify and network with similar initiatives and projects. By doing so, the consortium will be able to exchange knowledge and create synergies with other relevant organizations in the field.

- ❖ **KPI's:** >10 projects connected to MARINEWIND
- ❖ **Target:** EU and National Projects and initiatives
- ❖ **Date:** M12-36

4. CONCLUSIONS

Task 5.1 of work package 5 of the MARINEWIND project aims to improve its communication efforts. To achieve this goal, the project team has developed the MARINEWIND Strategic Communication and Dissemination Plan (SCDP).

The primary objective of the SCDP is to provide MARINEWIND partners with guidelines on how to perform communication and dissemination activities for the project. The plan outlines what messages will be delivered and what tools and channels will be used to reach the identified audiences.

The guidelines provided in the SCDP will be tracked throughout the project's lifetime, and adjustments will be made when necessary to ensure that the best methods are used to communicate the project's progress and outcomes.

By having a comprehensive SCDP, the MARINEWIND project team can ensure that all communication efforts are consistent, effective, and aligned with the project's objectives. This will also help the team to identify any gaps in communication and take corrective actions promptly.

In summary, the MARINEWIND Strategic Communication and Dissemination Plan is a crucial document that provides guidelines on how to communicate the project's progress and outcomes. The plan will be tracked and adjusted as necessary to ensure the most effective communication methods are used throughout the project's lifetime.

ANNEX I – PERFORMANCE INDICATOR LOG

ACTIVITY	KPI	SPECIFIC KPI	TARGET	DATE
Brand identity: Logo & Templates	#1 brand identity kit		All Stakeholders	M1
Project Website	#1 website	>3.000 visits >27 countries reached	All Stakeholders	M6
Social Media	#2 channels (LinkedIn and Twitter)	>5 social media campaigns, > 1.000 followers, > 500 posts	All Stakeholders	M6
Flyer, Roll up and Posters	#2 flyers, #2 roll-ups, >2 posters	500 flyers distributed in at least 5 languages included English (for the 5 Labs)	All Stakeholders	Version 1: M6, Version 2: M22
Infographics	>5 infographics	#1 factsheet of the Action Plan for public acceptance, #1 Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations in at least 5 languages included English (for the 5 Labs), >10 promotional banners.	All Stakeholders, in particular policymaker, civil society, businesses	M12
Multimedia Material	#1 promotional video, #2 video teasers		All Stakeholders	M12
Conferences & Events and publication	>6 speeches at events and conferences (live and online), >6 Articles in newspapers, magazines, television, or radio, >6 Press releases, #1 Final event	>6 Press releases to more than 10.000 contacts, #1 Final event to present MARINEWIND outcomes to the European Commission and other relevant stakeholders attended by at least 80 participants for the Quintuple Helix.	All Stakeholders	M12-36, Final event M34
Webinars	#2 webinars	#2 informative webinars in the 5 languages included English (for the 5 Labs) (>250 participants in total)	Policy makers and public authorities	M12-34
Stakeholders database	#1 database	>1.000 contacts	Partners' Networks, EU and National Projects and initiatives	M12
Clustering with other projects and initiatives	>10 projects connected to MARINEWIND		EU and National Projects and initiatives	M12-36

ANNEX II – EVENT PLANNING

EVENT NAME	DATE	VENUE
WindEurope Annual Event	25-27 April	Copenhagen, Denmark
OFFSHORE TECHNOLOGY CONFERENCE 2023	1-4 May	HOUSTON, TEXAS, USA
Pacific Offshore Wind Summit 2023	8-10 May	Sacramento, CA (US)
European Maritime Day (EMD) 2023	24-25 May	Brest, France
Lisbon Energy Summit & Exhibition 2023	30 May - 1 June	Lisbon, Portugal
WindEurope TECHNOLOGY WORKSHOP	1-2 June	Lyon, France
Floating Energy Systems Conference	8-9 June	Lisbon, Portugal
Global Offshore Wind 2023	14-15 June	London, UK
Seenergy 2023	20-21 June	Paris, France
European Sustainable Energy Week 2023	20-22 June	Brussels, Belgium
Offshore Europe	5-8 September	Aberdeen, Scotland
7th Conference on Wind Energy and Wildlife Impacts (CWW 2023)	18-22 September	Šibenik, Croatia
Offshore WINDPOWER 2023 Conference & Exhibition	3-4 October	Boston, MA, U.S.
Floating Offshore Wind	4-5 October	Aberdeen, Scotland
European Week for Regions and Cities	9-12 October	
Ocean Energy Europe Conference & Exhibition (OEE2023)	25-26 October	The Hague - The Netherlands
WINDMission Iberia 2023	5-6 November	Lisbon, Portugal
Marine Renewables Canada 2023 Conference	14-16 November	Ottawa ON, Canada
Offshore Energy Exhibition & Conference 2023	28-29 November	Amsterdam, The Netherlands
WavEC Seminar 2023	6 December	Lisbon, Portugal
EERA JP Wind		